

DAG development for salutogenic outcome – Breastfeeding

ESC-DAGs Decision Log

	<u>Variables</u>
Outcome	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
Exposure(s)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (One-to-one care during labour / vs. not one-to-one care during labour)
Control(s)	Gestational age Risk of hypoglycaemia Parity Mode of birth Maternal age Country of birth / ethnicity Pregnancy complications Birth weight
Mediator(s)	Labour complications Admission to NICU
Moderator(s)	Length of stay Peak TSB Phototherapy Early skin to skin contact after birth Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth Maternal level of education

IG Code (Figure 1)

Diagrams

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dag {
  bb="0,0,1,1"
  "Admission to NICU" [pos="0.591,0.329"]
  "Birth weight" [pos="0.425,0.205"]
  "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge" [outcome,pos="0.592,0.445"]
  "Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" [pos="0.646,0.627"]
  "Country of birth / ethnicity" [pos="0.411,0.652"]
  "Early skin to skin contact after birth" [pos="0.723,0.558"]
  "Gestational age" [pos="0.317,0.276"]
  "Labour complications" [pos="0.491,0.676"]
  "Length of stay" [pos="0.596,0.559"]
  "Maternal age" [pos="0.355,0.625"]
  "Maternal education" [pos="0.720,0.475"]
  "Mode of birth" [pos="0.308,0.592"]
  "Peak TSB" [pos="0.671,0.326"]
  "Pregnancy complications" [pos="0.489,0.589"]
  "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" [pos="0.500,0.269"]
  "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" [exposure,pos="0.359,0.446"]
  Parity [pos="0.276,0.528"]
  Phototherapy [pos="0.704,0.405"]
  "Admission to NICU" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
  "Birth weight" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
  "Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
  "Early skin to skin contact after birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Gestational age" -> "Birth weight"
  "Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
  "Gestational age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
  "Labour complications" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Labour complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
  "Length of stay" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Maternal age" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Maternal age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
  "Maternal education" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Mode of birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Mode of birth" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
  "Mode of birth" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
  "Peak TSB" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Pregnancy complications" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
  "Pregnancy complications" -> "Length of stay"
  "Pregnancy complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
  "Pregnancy complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
  "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
}

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DAG Code (adapted, Figure 2)

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"Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Admission to NICU"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Length of stay"
Parity -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
Parity -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
Phototherapy -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
}
dag {
bb="0,0,1,1"
"Admission to NICU" [pos="0.591,0.329"]
"Birth weight" [pos="0.425,0.205"]
"Breastfeeding at hospital discharge" [outcome,pos="0.592,0.445"]
"Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" [pos="0.646,0.621"]
"Country of birth / ethnicity" [pos="0.411,0.652"]
"Early skin to skin contact after birth" [pos="0.723,0.558"]
"Gestational age" [pos="0.317,0.276"]
"Labour complications" [pos="0.491,0.676"]
"Length of stay" [pos="0.596,0.559"]
"Maternal age" [pos="0.355,0.625"]
"Maternal education" [pos="0.720,0.475"]
"Mode of birth" [pos="0.308,0.592"]
"Peak TSB" [pos="0.671,0.326"]
"Pregnancy complications" [pos="0.489,0.589"]
"Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" [pos="0.500,0.269"]
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" [exposure,pos="0.359,0.446"]
Parity [pos="0.276,0.528"]
Phototherapy [pos="0.704,0.405"]
"Admission to NICU" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Birth weight" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Early skin to skin contact after birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Gestational age" -> "Birth weight"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Gestational age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Labour complications" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Labour complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Length of stay" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Maternal age" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Maternal age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Maternal education" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Mode of birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Mode of birth" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Mode of birth" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Peak TSB" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Length of stay"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Admission to NICU"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Length of stay"
Parity -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
Parity -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
Phototherapy -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
}

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Adjustment set and adjusted DAG (Figure 3)

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dag {
bb="0,0,1,1"
"Admission to NICU" [pos="0.591,0.329"]
"Birth weight" [adjusted,pos="0.425,0.205"]
"Breastfeeding at hospital discharge" [outcome,pos="0.592,0.445"]
"Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" [pos="0.646,0.621"]
"Country of birth / ethnicity" [adjusted,pos="0.411,0.652"]
"Early skin to skin contact after birth" [pos="0.723,0.558"]
"Gestational age" [adjusted,pos="0.317,0.276"]
"Labour complications" [adjusted,pos="0.491,0.676"]
"Length of stay" [pos="0.596,0.559"]
"Maternal age" [adjusted,pos="0.355,0.625"]
"Maternal education" [pos="0.720,0.475"]
"Mode of birth" [adjusted,pos="0.308,0.592"]
"Peak TSB" [pos="0.671,0.326"]
"Pregnancy complications" [adjusted,pos="0.489,0.589"]
"Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" [adjusted,pos="0.500,0.269"]
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" [exposure,pos="0.359,0.446"]
Parity [adjusted,pos="0.276,0.528"]
Phototherapy [pos="0.704,0.405"]
"Admission to NICU" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Birth weight" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Early skin to skin contact after birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
}

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"Gestational age" -> "Birth weight"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Gestational age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Labour complications" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Labour complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Length of stay" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Maternal age" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Maternal age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Maternal education" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Mode of birth" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Mode of birth" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Mode of birth" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Peak TSB" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Length of stay"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia --> Feeding intervention" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Admission to NICU"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)" -> "Length of stay"
Parity -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
Parity -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) (postnatal unit)"
Phototherapy -> "Breastfeeding at hospital discharge"
}

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Number of Edges assessed 32
Number of Edges reversed 0
Number of Edges retained 32
Number of Edges deleted 0

Figure 1 Integrated DAG based on literature and expert knowledge

Figure 2 Adapted DAG after edge assessment

Figure 3 Adapted DAG after edge assessment & adjusted for confounding variables [Gestational age; Birth weight; Risk of hypoglycaemia; Parity; Mode of birth; Maternal age; Country of birth / ethnicity; Labour complications; Pregnancy complications]

IG Edges

Edge ID (#)	Variable From	Variable To	Decision	Theory and Reference
1 (page 6)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(1–4)
2 (page 7)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Admission to NICU	Retain	(1,5)
3 (page 9)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Length of stay	Retain	(4)
4 (page 11)	Gestational age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(6)
5 (page 13)	Gestational age	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(7)
6 (page 14)	Gestational age	Birth weight	Retain	(8)
7 (page 15)	Birth weight	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(7,9)
8 (page 17)	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(1,10–12)
9 (page 19)	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(6,16)
10 (page 21)	Admission to NICU	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(17)
11 (page 23)	Peak TSB	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(18–20)
12 (page 25)	Phototherapy	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(21–23)
13 (page 27)	Maternal education	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(24,25)
14 (page 29)	Early skin to skin contact after birth	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(17,26,27)
15 (page 31)	Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(3,17)
16 (page 33)	Length of stay	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(28,29)
17 (page 35)	Pregnancy complications	Length of stay	Retain	(30)
18 (page 36)	Pregnancy complication	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(7,16,31,32)
19 (page 38)	Labour complications	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(17,25,33,34)
20 (page 41)	Labour complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(35–37)
21 (page 43)	Pregnancy complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(38,39)
22 (page 45)	Country of birth/ethnicity	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(40)
23 (page 46)	Country of birth/ethnicity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(41,42)
24 (page 48)	Maternal age	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(25,43)
25 (page 50)	Maternal age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(44)
26 (page 51)	Mode of birth	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(17,43)
27 (page 53)	Mode of birth	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(31)
28 (page 55)	Mode of birth	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(45)
29 (page 56)	Parity	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(17,24,25)
30 (page 59)	Parity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(46–48)
31 (page 60)	Birth weight	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(49)
32 (page 62)	Pregnancy complications	Breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Retain	(43,50)

Translation

Edge ID (1)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Yes – DAG Neonatal Outcome – Dani
Measurement	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	The relation is plausible
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	More registered staff leads to a higher proportion of exclusive breastfeeding (13) Lack of adequate staff and time leads to minor breastfeeding support and more artificial feeding (2,3) Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge was higher (88% vs. 78%, $p=0.048$) in infants born in the midwife than in the obstetrician-led centre(4)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit	

	Counterfactual question	What is the effect of low vs. high proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit on exclusive breastfeeding?	
	Hypothesised outcome	It is expected that if the proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit is high, more time for support and breastfeeding information would be available and this would have a positive effect on the number of newborns exclusively breastfed	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain	

Edge ID (2)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Admission to NICU	Part of if yes – DAG Neonatal Outcome – Dani
Measurement	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.		
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes

	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	The proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit precedes possible admission to NICU
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	The proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit shows a possible causal relationship with NICU admission.
		Reverse direction	No	Admission to NICU of newborn has no influence on nurse-to-patient ratio on maternity ward
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	A study states that with more registered staff, lower rates of admission to the neonatal unit were found.(13) The analysis of a review showed no overall difference between the groups in terms of admission of the infant to special care or neonatal intensive care. But there were some included studies where it was significant (5).
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit	
		Counterfactual question	If all newborns received low	

			proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit, would the likelihood of admission to NICU be different?	
	Hypothesised outcome		We expect that newborns who received low proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit would have a higher likelihood of admission to NICU	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		A low proportion of nurse-to-patient ratio might lead to an overwhelming workload and missed care.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA	
	Conclusion		Retain	

Edge ID (3)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Length of stay	Part of if yes – DAG Neonatal Outcome – Dani
	Measurement	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	Length of stay in days	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes

	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Nurse-to-patient ratio exists before length of stay
		Reverse direction	Yes	Length of stay may have an influence on nurse-to-patient ratio
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that high nurse-to-patient ratio leads to better outcomes and shortens length of stay
		Reverse direction	Yes	Long length of stay might lead to an increased number of patients on the unit, which could influence the following nurse-to-patient ratio.
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Duration of hospital stay was higher in the obstetrician- than in the midwife-led centre (3.1 ± 1.8 vs 2.6 ± 0.8 days, $P = .008$) (4)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit	
		Counterfactual question	How would different proportions of target nurse-to-patient ratios during hospital stay affect length of stay?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect lower proportions of target nurse-to-patient ratios during hospital stay would lead to longer length of stay	

	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Low target nurse-to-patient ratios lead to worse outcomes and more missed care	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (4)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Gestational age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Birth
Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age should logically stand before nurse-to-patient ratios on postnatal unit
	Reverse direction	No	It is not plausible that the proportion of nurse-to-patient ratios would influence the gestational age of the pregnancy.
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age could influence nurse-to-patient ratios. Newborns with lower gestational ages might require more staffing.
	Reverse direction	No	

	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Late preterm infants are at high risk for medical complications such as respiratory issues, hyperbilirubinemia, poor feeding, temperature instability and infections. Frequent assessments are needed, influencing staffing exposure. (6)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	All women have gestational age of 36 weeks or less	
		Counterfactual question	Would there be a different nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit if the gestational age of all women in labour was 36 or less weeks?	
		Hypothesised outcome	A higher nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit may be required to address specific risks associated with late preterm gestations.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Lower gestational ages may present complications requiring increased care to manage potential risks.	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	

	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (5)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Gestational age	Risk of hypoglycaemia	No
	Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age precedes birth of newborn with possible risk of hypoglycaemia
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that gestational age (preterm) has an influence on risk of hypoglycaemia
		Reverse direction	No	Risk of hypoglycaemia does not affect gestational age
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Of 193 late preterm (35-37 weeks) newborns, 103 (54%) had hypoglycaemia, 39 (20%) had severe hypoglycaemia and 37 (19%) had recurrent hypoglycaemia (7)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different gestational ages, e.g. 36+0 weeks vs. 40+0 weeks	
		Counterfactual question	How would different gestational ages	

		affect the risk of hypoglycaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of hypoglycaemia in late preterm (gestational age of 36+0 weeks)	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Late preterm infants have an immature metabolism and lower glucagon stores	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain	

Edge ID (6)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Gestational age	Birth weight	Yes – IG DAG Birth
Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age influences development and therefore weight of fetus
	Reverse direction	No	Birth weight of baby is measured after birth when pregnancy and therefore gestational age is over. It cannot influence gestational age.
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that higher gestational ages

			result in higher birth weight due to longer period of fetal growth
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	They observed a clear increase in birth weight by gestational age for all term weeks. (8)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different gestational ages, e.g. 36+0 weeks vs. 40+0 weeks	
	Counterfactual question	How would different gestational ages affect birth weight?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher birth weight in term newborns (40+0 weeks) than in late preterm newborns (36+0 weeks)	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (7)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Birth weight	Risk of hypoglycaemia	
Measurement	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	

	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth weight precedes the risk of hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that birth weight affects the metabolism
	Reverse direction	No	Risk of hypoglycaemia does not affect birth weight
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Of 152 small newborns ($\leq 10^{\text{th}}$ percentile or $\leq 2500\text{g}$), 77 had hypoglycaemia (52%), of 133 large newborns, 61 had hypoglycaemia (47%) (7) The risk of neonatal hypoglycaemia increased significantly as the birth weight percentile increased, both in diabetic and non-diabetic pregnancies ($p < 0.0001$) (9)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Normal vs. high birth weight	
	Counterfactual question	Would the risk of hypoglycaemia differ in normal vs. high birth weight?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that newborns with high birth weight had an increased risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns with high birth weight	

			have an increased risk for hyperinsulinemia (often due to maternal diabetes)	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (8)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	No
	Measurement	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hypoglycaemia precedes nurse-to-patient ratio
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that newborns with risk of hypoglycaemia need more monitoring which requires a higher nurse-to-patient ratio
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	All newborns were breast or formula fed in the first hour after birth. Plasma glucose was measured 30min thereafter. If glucose was <25mg/L,

				<p>feeding had to be repeated immediately and glucose was rechecked 1h later. If glucose value stayed <25mg/dL, i.v. glucose was started. Plasma glucose monitoring was performed every 2-3 hours. This protocol presents the increased workload for staffing due to frequent interventions and monitoring. (11)</p> <p>The authors advocate accepting some degree of overtreatment to prevent long-term impairment from hypoglycaemia (10)</p>
		Reverse direction	No	<p>Influence of midwife staffing on risk of hypoglycaemia in newborns not yet scrutinized (13)</p> <p>Nurses were worried about bad outcomes for the baby due to less frequent assessments in the context of being too busy (12)</p>
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Risk of hypoglycaemia vs. No risk of hypoglycaemia.	

	Counterfactual question	How would the risk of hypoglycaemia affect nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit if there were numerous feeding interventions to prevent hypoglycaemia.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns with risk for hypoglycaemia need rigorous monitoring and feeding interventions to prevent hypoglycaemia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain	

Edge ID (9)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	
Measurement	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hypoglycaemia precedes exclusive

			breastfeeding at hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge has no influence on preceding risk of hypoglycaemia
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that risk of hypoglycaemia may have an influence on the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Regardless of the initial feeding method, most infants born to women with pregestational diabetes require supplementation. Even when medically necessary, in-hospital supplementation can hinder exclusive breastfeeding at discharge, though not completely. (16) Formula is unnecessary and may interfere with the establishment of normal breast feeding (6)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Risk vs. no risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Counterfactual question	How would the risk of hypoglycaemia affect exclusive breastfeeding at	

		hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a lower rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Supplemental feeding decreases the newborns' demand of breastmilk which on the other hand decreases milk production of mother and may have an influence on the mothers' confidence to exclusively breastfeeding	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (10)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Admission to NICU	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
Measurement		Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Admission to NICU happens before hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	Practice of exclusive breastfeeding at discharge cannot

			influence preceding NICU stay
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that newborns who were admitted to NICU may have issues with breastfeeding due to their possible health complications and separation from mother
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Admission to NICU was associated with not maintaining exclusive breastfeeding after discharge (aOR: 0.31; 95% CI: 0.19 – 0.52). (17)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	NICU admission vs. no NICU admission	
	Counterfactual question	How would the admission to NICU affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding would be lower in newborns who had been admitted to NICU	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Due to separation of the mother and potential health complications	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	

		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (11)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Peak TSB	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Part of it yes – DAG Neonatal Outcome – Dani
	Measurement	Measured transcutaneous bilirubin value from surveillance curve	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	If we look at breastfeeding at the time of discharge, the temporality is plausible.
		Reverse direction	No	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge cannot influence peak TSB that was measured during hospital stay
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	A high TSB is associated with sleepiness which might lead to less effective breastfeeding sessions which might decrease the rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	A high TSB may lead to supplementary feeding because of wanting to prevent fasting of the infant which has positive influence on

				<p>exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge (18,19)</p> <p>Hyperbilirubinaemia causes lethargy and poor feeding in some newborns which in turn reduces the frequency and duration of breastfeeding as well as milk production (20). This could lead to a lower rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.</p>
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	High vs. low peak TSB	
		Counterfactual question	How would different levels of peak TSB affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
		Hypothesised outcome	Higher peak TSB levels might reduce the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at discharge.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	A high TSB is associated with sleepiness which might lead to less effective breastfeeding sessions which might decrease the rate of exclusive	

			breastfeeding at hospital discharge.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (12)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Phototherapy	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Yes – DAG Neonatal Outcome – Dani
	Measurement	CHOP code for phototherapy	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Phototherapy precedes exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that phototherapy might interfere with breastfeeding routines and reduce the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	In a study, parents rated breastfeeding as a risk factor for neonatal jaundice and indicated that cessation of breastfeeding was a management option (22)

			<p>Phototherapy should preferably not be interrupted (21) which has influence on breastfeeding routines and might decrease the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge .</p> <p>Interrupting breastfeeding as part of therapy for hyperbilirubinemia is associated with a major increase in the frequency of stopping breastfeeding by one month (RR=1.79, 95% CI 1.04 to 3.06 (23)</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Phototherapy vs. no phototherapy	
	Counterfactual question	How would the intervention phototherapy affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that the intervention phototherapy might reduce the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at discharge.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Due to potential interruptions in breastfeeding routines and the	

		need for supplemental feeding.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (13)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Maternal education	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
Measurement	Variable not measured	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Maternal education precedes birth
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that higher education of mother is associated with more knowledge about the benefits of breastfeeding which may be motivating to exclusively breastfeed
	Reverse direction	No	Breastfeeding does not change mother's education level
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	High maternal education is associated with an increased likelihood of breastfeeding (RR 2.28 [95% CI 1.92-2.70]) (24)

			Mothers with higher education were 25% less likely to exclusively breastfeed at hospital discharge compared to mothers with secondary education or less (AOR 0.75; 95% CI 0.59, 0.97) (25)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different education levels: no high school vs. university degree	
	Counterfactual question	Would the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding be different among different education levels?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that women with higher education would have a higher likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Women of higher education have more knowledge about the benefits of breastfeeding and more support and resources for breastfeeding than women of lower education	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	

	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (14)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Early skin to skin contact after birth	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
Measurement	Not measured	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Skin to skin contact happens directly after birth and precedes breastfeeding at hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that early skin to skin contact promotes bonding which encourages mother to breastfeed which increases the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Exclusive breastfeeding during hospital stay was higher in mothers who experienced skin-to-skin contact after birth for 1 to 15 minutes (OR 1.376; 95% CI 1.189-1.593), 16 to 30 minutes (OR 1.665; 95% CI, 1.468-1.888), 31 to 59 minutes (OR 2.357; 95% CI, 2.061-

			2.695), and more than 1 hour (OR 3.145; 95% CI, 2.905-3.405). (26,27)
			Infants with skin-to-skin contact after birth were more likely to be exclusively breastfed at hospital discharge than infants without skin-to-skin contact after birth (OR 2.94 95% CI [2.17 -3.97] (17)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Early skin to skin contact vs. no early skin to skin contact	
	Counterfactual question	How would early skin to skin contact affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that early skin to skin contact would increase the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Early skin to skin contact releases oxytocin in mother and child which helps initiate breastfeeding	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	

		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (15)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
	Measurement	First feeding entry in surveillance curve (if breastfeeding).	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	First breastfeeding happens before hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge cannot influence the past breastfeeding initiation 1 hour after birth
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth supports the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Missed breastfeeding within 1 hour of birth is negatively associated with the exclusive breast milk feeding rate (p < 0.05) (3) Breastfeeding initiation within 1

			hour after birth is positively associated with breastfeeding at hospital discharge (OR 4.29; 95% CI [3.20 – 5.75]) (17)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour vs. later initiation	
	Counterfactual question	How would breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth would increase the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Early initiation of breastfeeding stimulates milk production and bonding between mother and child	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (16)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Length of stay	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	Yes – DAG Neonatal Outcome – Dani
Measurement	Length of stay in days	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Usual, length of stay is first and has an impact on the ability to breastfeed.
	Reverse direction	No	Rarely but possible: The ability of breastfeeding could influence the length of stay.
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Reasonable thinking that longer stay, helps in getting more practice, information and help with breastfeeding.
	Reverse direction	No	Breastfeeding difficulties could have an influence on the length of stay and prolong it.
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Successful breastfeeding needs practice and time, lactation process starts only a few days after birth – therefore chance of exclusive breastfeeding higher with longer length of stay. (28) Though a study concluded: Maternal characteristics may be more important predictors of the duration of breastfeeding than

			length of stay in hospital after birth. (29)
	Reverse direction	No	Complications in breastfeeding could theoretically lead to longer length of stay. Nevertheless, due to the DRG System (Diagnosis Related Groups) in Switzerland's health system, it is unlikely that a women will stay longer in a hospital after birth because of breastfeeding issues.
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Long vs. short length of stay	
	Counterfactual question	How would different lengths of stay affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge to be lower after a short length of stay.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	A shorter length of stay provides less opportunities for educating interventions about breastfeeding from midwives/nurses and less time to establish a breastfeeding routine	

	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (17)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Pregnancy complications	Length of stay	No
Measurement	ICD Diagnoses, if at least one is present, it is a yes.	Length of stay in days	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Pregnancy complications precede length of stay
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that pregnancy complications can lead to a longer length of stay due to the need for further medical care
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Women with gestational diabetes experienced longer length of stay (30)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Pregnancy complications vs. no complications	
	Counterfactual question	How would pregnancy complications or its absence affect length of stay?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that women with	

			pregnancy complications would have longer lengths of stay.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Pregnancy complications require monitoring and further medical interventions	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (18)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Pregnancy complications	Risk of hypoglycaemia	
Measurement	ICD Diagnoses, if at least one is present, it is a yes.	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Pregnancy complications happen during or after labour and before risk of hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	No	Risk of hypoglycaemia cannot influence past pregnancy complications
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that pregnancy complications like diabetes can lead to complications for the newborn which has influence on its glucose metabolism

	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	<p>Infants of diabetic mothers are at higher risk of hypoglycaemia (7,31)</p> <p>Maternal hypertension (OR 3.07, 95% CI 1.51–6.30, p = 0.002) was the sole risk factor for neonatal hypoglycaemia (32)</p> <p>Of the 134 infants of diabetic mothers whose early feeding was breast feeding, hypoglycaemia affected 30% which was corrected with oral feedings in 78% of the cases (16)</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Pregnancy complications vs. absence of pregnancy complications	
	Counterfactual question	How would the presence of pregnancy complications affect the likelihood of neonatal hypoglycaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of neonatal hypoglycaemia.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Maternal diabetes leads to high fetal glucose levels with compensatory hyperinsulinemia. After separation	

			from mother, the hyperinsulinemia in the newborns' metabolism causes neonatal hypoglycaemia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (19)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Labour complications	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
Measurement	ICD Diagnosis and CHOP codes to identify the complications. Dichotomised, yes/no, if at least one of the conditions is present.	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Labour complications occur during or shortly after birth and can influence process of establishing a routine in breastfeeding which may have an influence on exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge cannot influence passed labour complications

	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that labour complications affect the mother's health and her ability to breastfeed, thus the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	<p>Women who had a postpartum haemorrhage had significantly fewer breastfeeding sessions on average ($\beta = -0.06$, p-value 0.01 (33) which might influence rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.</p> <p>General anaesthesia which is an indicator for labour complications was negatively associated with breastfeeding at hospital discharge OR 0.37 95% CI [0.20 – 0.68] (17)</p> <p>Maternal intrapartum complications were not associated with exclusive breastfeeding at discharge (OR 0.88, 95% CI [0.61 -1.32] (25)</p> <p>Transfusion of any blood product (after postpartum</p>

			haemorrhage) was associated with a lower rate of breastfeeding (OR 0.82 [95%CI 0.730.93] (34)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of labour complications, e.g. postpartum haemorrhage	
	Counterfactual question	How would postpartum haemorrhages affect the rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a lower rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Woman may suffer from physical and emotional distress after postpartum haemorrhage as well as from delayed lactogenesis which may influence the process of establishing a routine in breastfeeding which may have an impact on the rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	

	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (20)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Labour complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	
Measurement	ICD Diagnosis and CHOP codes to identify the complications. Dichotomised, yes/no, if at least one of the conditions is present.	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Labour complications occur during birth before stay on postnatal unit with its staffing exposure
	Reverse direction	No	Staffing on postnatal unit cannot influence passed labour
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that a mother with labour complications requires more monitoring and nursing interventions during postnatal stay, thus labour complications have an influence on staffing
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	High-grade perineal tear requires postnatal surgery which necessitates increased nursing interventions. (35) A postpartum haemorrhage requires more staffing on postnatal

			unit for augmented monitoring, pain management and emotional support as a postpartum haemorrhage can be traumatising for the mother (risk for posttraumatic stress syndrome). (36,37)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of labour complications	
	Counterfactual question	How would presence of labour complications affect proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that the presence of labour complications would necessitate a higher proportion of nurse-to-patient ratio to provide adequate care.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Women with labour complications require more monitoring and nursing interventions to ensure patient safety	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (21)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Pregnancy complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	
Measurement	ICD Diagnoses, if at least one is present, it is a yes.	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Pregnancy complications occur during pregnancy before stay on postnatal unit
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that mothers with pregnancy complications require more care during postnatal period, thus influencing staffing exposure
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Women with diabetes need augmented blood sugar monitoring and nursing interventions after birth due to higher risk of hypoglycaemia which has influence on staffing exposure (39) Women who have experienced eclampsia require augmented care on intensive care unit before being transferred to the postnatal ward.

			After transfer on postnatal unit, they require close monitoring and enhanced nursing interventions to ensure their safety which has influence on staffing exposure (38)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of pregnancy complication	
	Counterfactual question	How would pregnancy complications affect the proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during the hospital stay on the postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher nurse-to-patient ratio.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Mothers with pregnancy complications require increased monitoring, nursing interventions and support for recovery after birth	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (22)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Country of birth/ethnicity	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	
Measurement	Citizenship & language	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Citizenship of mother stands before birth and breastfeeding of newborn
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that the citizenship of mother with its cultural, social and economic influences could affect the likelihood of breastfeeding at hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge cannot change citizenship of mother
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Mothers from all regions apart from West Europe were more likely to exclusively breastfeed their children at hospital discharge (40)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different birth countries of mother	
	Counterfactual question	How would different birth countries of mother affect the likelihood of exclusive	

			breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome		We expect that women of some countries would be less likely to exclusive breastfeed at hospital discharge	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Cultural beliefs and support on breastfeeding may vary between countries which can influence the mothers' decision and ability to breastfeed	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (23)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Country of birth/ethnicity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	No
Measurement	Citizenship & language	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth of woman happens before Staffing exposure on postnatal unit
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Immigrated mothers may have less knowledge about health care system

			and might request less care due to language barriers
		Reverse direction	No
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes
			Immigrant women are more often unaware of postpartum services, so they are unlikely to ask for support which has influence on staffing exposure (41)
			Immigrant women experienced difficulties with nurses, including communication barriers, lack of empathy, perceived bias due to accents, and feeling disrespected or not taken seriously (42) Thus, they might refrain from seeking support from nurses on postpartum unit.
		Reverse direction	No
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different country of birth/ethnicity (immigrants vs. native-born women)
		Counterfactual question	How would demand on staffing on postnatal unit differ if the mother's country of birth/ethnicity were different?
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect that there would be a higher staffing demand if all mothers on postnatal ward

		were of foreign origin.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Intercultural communitive barriers might require special trained staff	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain	

Edge ID (24)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Maternal age	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
Measurement	Age in years	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Maternal age is known before hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that women of different ages have different levels of experience, confidence and support which may have an impact on exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Mothers age showed no association with exclusive

			breastfeeding at hospital discharge in multivariable analysis (OR 0.98, 95% CI [0.96 – 1.00]) (25)
			Older women had higher odds of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge (OR 1.26, 95% CI 1.23–1.30 for 10-year increments) (43)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different ages of women, e.g. 25 vs. 35 years old	
	Counterfactual question	How would different ages of women affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect women of older age to have a higher likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Women with older age may have more support, confidence and knowledge about breastfeeding	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	

	Conclusion	Retain		
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Edge ID (25)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Maternal age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)
	Measurement	Age in years	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.
		Question	Answer (Y/N)
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes
		Reverse direction	No
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes
		Reverse direction	No
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes
		Reverse direction	No

	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different maternal ages	
		Counterfactual question	How would different maternal ages affect the proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during the hospital stay on the postnatal unit?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect that certain age groups require higher or lower nurse-to-patient ratios due to varying levels of care needs.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Younger mothers might need more educational and emotional support while older mothers might have more medical complications requiring closer monitoring.	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (26)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Mode of birth	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
	Measurement	ICD Diagnoses and CHOP codes to define mode of birth.	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes

	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth precedes hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge cannot influence previous mode of birth
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that mode of birth has an influence on breastfeeding initiation and routines which may affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Instrumental delivery, emergency and planned caesarean were negatively associated with exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge. (17) Women with either a planned caesarean delivery (50%, OR 0.56, 95% CI 0.52–0.60) or an unplanned caesarean delivery (48%, OR 0.48, 95% CI 0.44–0.51) were less likely than women with spontaneous vaginal deliveries to exclusively breastfeed (68%). (43)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different modes of birth (e.g., vaginal	

			birth vs. caesarean section)
	Counterfactual question		How would different modes of birth affect the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?
	Hypothesised outcome		We expect that vaginal births might be associated with higher rates of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge compared to caesarean sections.
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Vaginal births mostly allow immediate skin to skin contact for breastfeeding initiation which supports the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (27)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Mode of birth	Risk of hypoglycaemia	No
Measurement	ICD Diagnoses and CHOP codes to define mode of birth.	Feeding intervention to	

		prevent hypoglycaemia	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Mode of birth precedes risk of hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that mode of delivery has an influence on risk of hypoglycaemia due to different timing of first breastfeeding or differences in stress during labour
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction		Caesarean section (OR 2.38, 95% CI 1.56 – 3.65) was associated with an increased risk for neonatal hypoglycaemia (31)
	Reverse direction		
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different modes of birth (e.g., vaginal birth vs. caesarean section)	
	Counterfactual question	How would different modes of birth affect the risk of hypoglycaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that caesareans might be associated with higher rates of hypoglycaemia.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Vaginal births mostly allow immediate skin to skin contact and early initiation of breastfeeding while caesareans might lead to separation from mother and child	

			which delays initiation of breastfeeding which increases risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (28)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Mode of birth	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	No
Measurement	ICD Diagnoses and CHOP codes to define mode of birth.	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth precedes stay on postnatal ward
	Reverse direction	No	Staffing on postnatal ward cannot influence past mode of birth
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that different modes of birth have influence on staffing exposure on postnatal ward due to different needs of care and support
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	For woman after caesarean, intensive medical care is more often required than after a vaginal birth.

			(45)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different modes of birth (e.g. vaginal birth vs. caesarean)	
	Counterfactual question	How would different modes of birth affect the staffing exposure on the postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that woman after caesarean require higher staffing ratios due to increased medical needs.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Women after caesarean need more intensive monitoring due to potential complications like thrombosis	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (29)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Parity	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
Measurement	Parity, number of children born before (from BFS data).	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes

	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Parity is known before exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that multiparous women who already experienced breastfeeding may have higher rates of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	In univariable analysis, primiparous women were more likely to exclusively breastfeed at hospital discharge than nulliparous women (OR 1.28, 95% CI [1.04 – 1.56]). The multivariable analysis showed no significance for an association between parity and exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge (OR 1.13, 95% CI [0.86 – 1.47]). (25)
				A meta-analysis showed a high heterogeneity in the studies examining the effect of parity and breastfeeding initiation [breastfeeding in the birth hospitalisation period of up to 1 week after birth] and the summary RR was nonsignificant.

			<p>However, multiparity was positively related to continuation of breastfeeding [from 1 month of age until 1 year] (24)</p> <p>Multiparous women were more likely to breastfeed their newborn at hospital discharge than primiparous women. (17)</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Primiparity vs. multiparity	
	Counterfactual question	How would different statuses of parity affect the rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that multiparous women might have higher rates of exclusive breastfeeding at discharge.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Multiparous women are more experienced with breastfeeding and may have more confidence.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (30)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Parity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	No
Measurement	Parity, number of children born before (from BFS data).	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Parity exists before stay on postnatal unit and its staffing exposure
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that multiparous women are more experienced with postnatal care and may need less support than nulliparous women
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Primiparous women required more postnatal support from midwives than multiparous women. (48) Multiparity is associated with lower risk of adverse birth outcomes (47) which may require less need of postnatal care. Nulliparous women are at higher risk of emergency caesarean than multiparous women (46), which may require more frequent postnatal care.
	Reverse direction	No	

	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Primiparity vs. multiparity	
		Counterfactual question	How would different statuses of parity affect staffing exposure on postnatal ward?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect that primiparous women need more care and support than multiparous women	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Primiparous women are at higher risk for labour complications and may need more care and support after birth which influences staffing exposure	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion		Retain	

Edge ID (31)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Birth weight	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	No
	Measurement	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth weight is measured directly after birth before staffing exposure on postnatal unit

	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Low birth weight is associated with a higher risk of complications and requires more monitoring which could influence staffing exposure on postnatal unit
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns with low and high birth weight require additional monitoring (glucose management, vital signs), feeding assistance and further interventions (temperature management) (49) which necessitates a higher nurse-to-patient ratio
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high birth weight	
	Counterfactual question	How would different birth weights affect staffing exposure on postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that newborns with low and high birth weights would require higher staffing ratios due to increased medical and care needs.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns with low and high birth weight are more likely to suffer from complications and require additional monitoring,	

			feeding support and further medical interventions.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (32)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Pregnancy complications	Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge	No
	Measurement	ICD Diagnoses, if at least one is present, it is a yes.	Feeding of newborn during the last 24h before discharge.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Pregnancy complications have occurred during pregnancy before birth of newborn and discharge from hospital.
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that pregnancy complications can affect breastfeeding due to health problems of mother and newborn and thus the likelihood of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns of mothers with gestational diabetes

			<p>were less likely to be exclusively breastfed at discharge. (50)</p> <p>Women without pregnancy complications such as diabetes and hypertensive disorders were more likely to exclusively breastfeed their newborns at discharge (aOR 1.10, 95% CI 1.06–1.14). (43)</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of pregnancy complications, e.g. gestational diabetes	
	Counterfactual question	How would gestational diabetes affect the rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a lower rate of exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Mothers and newborns may suffer from health issues which may disrupt breastfeeding routines.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	

		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

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